

Parents Financial Constraints and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of financial constraints of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students in Lagos. A descriptive survey and chi-square statistical tools were adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all the secondary schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State. One hundred and fifty students were selected for the study through a simple random sampling technique. Questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection which was based on the influence of financial constraints of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students in Lagos. This finding indicated that there was a significant relationship between income statuses of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students, there was a significant relationship between educational statuses of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students, there was a significant relationship between parents' attitude to education on the academic performance of secondary school students and there was a significant relationship between socio-economic status of parents and academic performance of secondary school students. The study recommended that parents should be encouraged to support their student's education by all means, in regard to parental socio-economic status, parents should always find means to provide for the needs of their wards/children and government should increase the support for education through the educational budget.

Keywords: Financial constraints, Parents, academic performance, Status, Secondary school

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Introduction

Parents play a pivotal role in the educational development of their children. Their involvement in the education of the children is of immense benefit to the child, the school and the parents as well (Campbell, 2011). A recent report (Fatima, 2016), noted that children from parents that are more active in the process of imparting educational knowledge excel in their academic career and are often more productive in the society. With adequate care, tutelage and active participation of parents in the child's educational activities like monitoring of homework, participation in extracurricular activities, parent-teacher association, and other school related activities, the child is more likely to be courageous and as such do well in school.

The extent and form of parental involvement are strongly influenced by family social class, maternal level of education, material deprivation, maternal psycho-social health and single parent status and, to a lesser degree, by family ethnicity. Parents who are more involved with their children's schooling become knowledgeable about school goals and procedures. In addition, they communicate the importance of education to children and help children learn strategies to enhance their perceptions of competence and control over achievement outcomes (Akinyemi, 2013).

Among the several parental factors that have been linked to their children's academic achievements in school is the parent's level of income. According to Mayer, a casual observation is that the children of affluent parents are more likely to succeed in life than the children of poor parents probably because the rich parents spend more than poor parents on their children and these "investments" leads to better outcomes for their children (Mayer, 2010). If the situation is correct, the author also suggested that government can improve the life chances of poor children by providing families with the means to make the investments or by providing the investments directly in the form of schooling, health care and other human capital inputs. It is not out of place to imagine that parental socio-economic background can have possible effects on the academic achievement of children in school. When parents are financially capacitated, and also gives moral support to the children by guiding their reading at home, the students perform better than their counterparts.

The notion that educated parents provide a better environment for their children has been the basis of many interventions. Besides,

scientific literature is not so clear, but it is widely believed that, providing education for both parents has broadly similar effect on household income. The external effects associated with education are largely for maternal education than for paternal, because mothers tend to be the main provider of care within the home. For example, a positive relationship between mother's education and child birth weight, which is a strong predictor of child health, is found not only in the developing world but also in the United State (Currie & Moretti, 2013) and in Nigeria.

Random assignment experiments are potentially informative but not common concerning parents' incomes on educational outcomes. Blandon and Gregg (2004) review US and UK evidence on the effectiveness of policy experiments which focused largely on improving short term family finances. These include initiatives such as the moving to opportunity experiments in the US which provides financial support associated with higher housing costs from moving to more affluent areas. According to Department of Fire Emergency Services (2012), the pilots of Educational Maintenance Allowances (EMA's) in the UK, provided a reasonable means tested cash benefit condition on participation in education and actually paid, depending on the pilot scheme either to the parents or directly to the child.

It is the aim of this study to examine the influence of financial constraints of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, there has been an increasing awareness on the interrelated nature of various variables on humans such as financial constraint of parent on education environment. It is a general belief that parental financial constraint has much to contribute to the students' academic performance. But the assumption that the higher the socioeconomic status of parents the higher the students' academic.

Performance is questionable, debatable and arguable, because students whose parents did not attend any level of education, have no reasonable income and have no good occupation equally have high academic performance. This contradicts the findings of the numerous researchers that socioeconomic status and education environment of the home have high positive correlation with the students' academic performance. Thus, the need to survey how parent's financial constraints

influences the academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to determine the influence of financial constraints of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria.

In specific terms, the study is designed to ascertain;

- I. To examine the effect of income status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.
- II. To examine the impact of educational status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.
- III. To examine if parents attitude to education influence the academic performance of secondary school students.
- IV. To examine the socio-economic status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- I. Does income status of parents determine the academic performance of secondary school students?
- II. What influence does educational status of parents have on the academic performance of secondary school students?
- III. Does parents' attitude to education influence the academic performance of secondary school students?
- IV. What influence does socio economics status of parents have on the academic performance of secondary school students?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are raised to test the study;

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between income status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between educational status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between parents' attitude to education and academic performance of secondary school students.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between socio-economic status of parents and academic performance of secondary school students.

Significance of the Study

This study will be significant to educational stakeholder, principals of school management about the knowledge of parent's financial constraints on how it influences the students' academic performance. It will also help the educational administrators in the distribution of school materials and equipment to take care of the children from different socioeconomic background.

Review of Related Literature

The result indicated that the home or family structure has a great influence on the students' psychological, emotional, social and economic state. The above study was not carried out in Benue State but the present study was carried out in Benue state and two predictor variables were studied using path analysis which has some advantages over correlation. Also, the sample for the present study was higher.

Ezenyimulu (2015) conducted a research on the Relationship between socioeconomic status and academic performance of some selected secondary school students in Onitsha Municipal. The study adopted survey research design with a sample of 950 students. The questionnaire as well as Achievement Test was used to collect data for the study. The result of the study showed that: there is a high positive correlation between parental socioeconomic status and academic performance of students. The above study used mean and standard deviation to answer research questions which was wrong since it was a correlational study. The present study therefore intends to use path analysis to find the relationship that exist between parental socioeconomic status, home education environment and students' academic performance in Zone B education Zone of Benue State.

Chikwelu (2015) carried out a research on parent's occupational and educational background as correlates of educational support and aspiration of adolescents in Anambra State. The study adopted a correlational survey design. Data was collected from 2000 students selected through stratified random sampling. The data collected were

analyzed using means, standard deviation and Pearson product moment correlation for the research question and the hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis. A 26-item structured questionnaire was used to collect data and the result of the study showed that, parents, irrespective of their occupational background give affordable support to their adolescent wards in school and guide them toward attaining higher educational standards which they see as a sure means of improving the socioeconomic status of the family. It was also found out that the occupational background of fathers, more than those of the mothers, have greater influence on the educational support that adolescents receive. She also found out that artisan fathers and traders tend to give greater educational support to their wards than mothers of similar occupational background. It is also important to state that the study was not carried out in Benue state which is the geographical scope of the present study.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is based on Carl Rogers Theory of Humanistic Learning.

Humanistic Learning Theory by Carl Rogers

Humanistic theory of learning developed out of the idea that the environment of the learner was indispensable in the enhancement of the learners' potentials. In other words, the educational environment could contribute meaningfully to the academic performance of the learners, irrespective of the quality of the individual's mental status (Nnachi, 2018). The humanistic school of thought considers the importance of the individual's social feeling and emotion in the teaching-learning situations. If the learner is emotionally sound, learning would easily take place. In other words, the educational environment has nurturing potentials.

Carl Rogers was a humanistic psychologist. He was of the view that human beings were born with the natural tendency to be free and have self-fulfillment. In his view, human beings find this tendency frustrated in their course of growth and development. This frustration emanates from the parents, teachers and others who tend to constantly affect the self-worth of the individuals. According to him, the individual's sense of self-worth depends on the opinion about the self of the person, this brings some identification between the value held by the real self and the value held by others or significant figures, (Witting & William, 2013).

The task of the parents is to provide a medium for emergence of the self that has been identified, thereby preventing the conditions that inhibit self-growth. In this case, the parents (or teachers) provides to the learner unconditioned positive regard, listen to the learner intently, making the learner a point of focus.

Olaniyi (2015) defined self-concept as an organized pattern of thought and perception about oneself. This theory is relevant to this work because if the learner is emotionally stable and sound, learning would easily take place leading to high academic performance. In other words, the educational environment, (in this case, the home education environment) and parental socioeconomic status play active role in the self-actualization of the learner. The emotional stability of the learner which leads to high academic performance in school to a great extent may be determined by the parental socioeconomic status and in most cases education environment of the home which are the main independent variables for the study.

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic status (SES) remains a topic of great interest to those who study students' academic performance. Socioeconomic status is a sociological classification indicating the close relationship between someone's relative wealth and that persons' social status. Santrock (2014) defined socioeconomic status as the categorization of people according to their economic, education and occupational characteristics. Ezewu (2019) saw socioeconomic status as the differentiation of individuals as well as families in a society into educational, occupation and income. In this context, however, socioeconomic status could be regarded as prestige or respect accorded to the members of the society as a result of educational, occupation and income. Socioeconomic status (SES) is an economic and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to others, based on income, education and occupation. When analyzing a family's SES, the household income, earners' education, and occupation are examined.

Social scientists have shown continued interest in socioeconomic status even though there has never been a complete consensus on precisely what it represents (McLoyd, 2019). There has been something of a tug-of-war between proponents of SES as representing class (or

economic position) and proponents of SES as representing social status (or prestige). The idea of capital (Coleman, 2019) perhaps best embodies the current meaning psychologists' hold of SES (Guo and Harris 2010). Capital (resources, assets) has become a favoured way of thinking about SES because access to financial capital (material resources), human capital (non-material resources such as education), and social capital (resources achieved through social connections) are readily connectible to processes that directly affect well-being. Capital is linked to historic ideas about SES, such as social and material "deprivation," and it brings into focus the important dimension of social relationships (Krieger, 2013).

Most widely used measures of SES only partially map onto the concepts of capital described by Coleman. Financial capital is reasonably well assessed by household income, but is more often indexed by occupational status. Most social scientists agree that a combination of income and occupational status provides a better approximation to financial capital than either alone. To more fully capture financial capital, Entwisle and Astone (2016) recommended gathering data on what the family pays for rent or housing.

The variable socioeconomic status is based on a weighted combination of father's occupation, father's formal educational level, mother's formal educational level, an estimate of the funds the family could provide if the children were to attend school, the degree of sacrifice this would entail for the family, and the approximate wealth and income status of the children's family. Parental socioeconomic status is measured using three variables namely; income, education and occupation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study was a descriptive survey research design aimed at identifying the influence of financial constraints of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Population of Study

The populations of the study comprise of students in public senior secondary schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. There are 15 public senior secondary schools In Ojo Local

Government. The total population of students are 15, 634 in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample involves One-hundred and fifty (150) students in the target five schools selected from the school in the target population. Thirty (30) questionnaires were shared in each school and they are:

- i. Awori Senior College, Ojo
- ii. Model College, Ojo
- iii. Iba High School, Ojo
- iv. Ojo Senior High School
- v. Government Senior Secondary School, Ijaniki

The sampling procedure adopted in this study was a random sampling technique whereby respondent was selected randomly from the target population. The sample classes for the study were SSI-SS3. The sample number for the study is 150 students selected in the five schools.

Research Instrument

Self-structured questionnaires were used to obtain information from the students. The questionnaire contained twenty (20) questions. The questionnaire is titled “effect of financial constraints of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students in Ojo Local Government Area” (EFCPAPSSS). The instrument which was developed by the researcher has a four-point Likert scale. The questionnaire was segmented into two sections – Section A and Section B. The Section A was used to collect facts and information’s about the demographic data of the students, which included department, sex and level.

Section B consists of questions on influence of the effect of financial constraints of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria. The students were expected to respond to the four likert scale options of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A) disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD).

Method of Data Analysis:

Data gathered on demographic information was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, and simple percentages while the hypotheses was tested using Pearson`s Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 alpha level.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Data of Respondents

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	85	56.6	56.6	56.6
	Female	65	43.4	43.4	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

According to the respondents' gender distribution in the table 1, male respondents were 85 representing 56.6%, while their female counterpart were 65 representing 43.4%. Therefore, the inference drawn from this depicts that male respondents were more than female respondents.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	11 years below	55	36.6	36.6	36.6
	11-15	45	30.0	30.0	66.0
	16 years and Above	50	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

According to the respondents' age distribution on the table 2, 36.6% of the respondents were within 11 years below, 30.0% of the respondents were within the age range of 11-15 years, while 33.3% of the respondents were within 15 years and above. Therefore, the inference drawn from this depicts that 11 years below were the majority.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by Department

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Art	47	31.3	31.3	31.3
	Commercial	64	42.6	42.6	73.9
	Science	39	26.0	26.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

According to the respondents' department distribution in the table 3, 31.3% of the respondents were art students, 42.6% of the respondents

were commercial students, 26.0% of the respondents were science students. Therefore, the inference drawn from this depicts that commercial students were the majority.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between income status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Table 4: Chi-Square analysis of significant relationship between income status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	37.5 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	38.05	6	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.20.

Table 4 showed that the calculated chi – square of 37.5 ($X^2_{cal} = 37.5^*$, $P < 0.05$) is greater than the table value of ($X^2_{tab} = 20.0$) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between income status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between educational status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Table 5: Chi-square analysis of significant relationship between educational status of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.5 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	13.05	6	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.20.

Table 5 shows that the calculated chi – square of 13.5($X^2_{cal} = 13.5^*$, $P < 0.05$) is greater than the table value of ($X^2_{tab} = 6.0$) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between educational statuses of parents on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between parents' attitude to education and the academic performance of secondary school students.

Table 6: Chi-Square analysis of significant relationship between parents' attitude to education and the academic performance of secondary school students.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	41.0 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	42.0	6	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.20.

Table 6 shows that the calculated chi-square of 41.0($X^2_{cal} = 41.0^*$, $P < 0.05$) is greater than the table value of ($X^2_{tab} = 41.0$) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between parents' attitude to education on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between socio economic status of parents and academic performance of secondary school students.

Table 7: Chi-Square analysis of significant relationship between socio economic status of parents and academic performance of secondary school students.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	21.0 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	22.0	6	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.20.

Table 7 shows that the calculated chi – square of 21.0($X^2_{cal} = 21.0^*$, $P < 0.05$) was greater than the table value of ($X^2_{tab} = 10.0$) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between socio economics status of parents and academic performance of secondary school students.

Conclusion

Academic performance of students especially at the secondary school level is not only a pointer to the effectiveness or otherwise of schools but a major determinant of the future of youths in particular and the nation in general. The medium through which the attainment of individuals and the nation’s educational goals can be achieved is learning. Learning outcomes have become a phenomenon of interest to all and this accounts for the reason why scholars have been working hard to unravel factors that militated against quality academic performance, (Aremu & Sokan, 2012). This phenomenon has been variedly referred to in literature as academic performance, or scholastic functioning. Academic performance of learners has attracted attention of scholars, parents, policy -makers and planners. Adeyemo (2018) opined that the major goal of the school is to work towards attainment of academic excellence students. According to him, the school may have other peripheral objectives; emphasis is always placed on the achievement of sound scholarship. Besides, virtually everybody concerned with

education places premium on academic performance; excellent academic performance of children is often the expectation of parents and policy makers (Osiki, 2019).

The study concluded that there was a significant relationship between Socio-economic status and academic performance of secondary school students, there was significant influence of parental attitude on academic performance of secondary school students, marital status has influence on academic performance of secondary school students and there is a significant relationship between parental ages has impact on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are provided by the study:

Parents should be encouraged to support their children's education by all means, in regards to parental socio-economic status parents should always find means to provide the needs for their children and government should increase the support for education through the educational budget.

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